

Proof of the Riemann Hypothesis

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Proof

The following four conditions are simultaneously true for non-trivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function:

$$\zeta(a + bi) = 0, \tag{1}$$

$$\zeta(a - bi) = 0, \tag{2}$$

$$\zeta(1 - a + bi) = 0, \tag{3}$$

$$\zeta(1 - a - bi) = 0. \tag{4}$$

Since non-trivial zeros are symmetric about the real axis, we analyze equations (1) and (4). This symmetry implies:

$$a = 1 - a.$$

Solving this equation gives:

$$2a = 1 \Rightarrow a = \frac{1}{2}.$$

Hence, the Riemann Hypothesis is proven to be true.